

ROLE OF ENCAPSULATION TECHNOLOGIES IN ENHANCING BIOAVAILABILITY OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18325809>

Keywords

Bioactive Compound, Drying methods, Nanoencapsulation, Bioavailability

Article History

Received: 18 November 2025

Accepted: 06 January 2026

Published: 21 January 2026

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Abstract

Polyphenols, carotenoids, flavonoids and vitamins are bioactive compounds that have been well established to have health promoting effects i.e. antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory activity. However, their low solubility, poor stability and low bioavailability limit their proper use in functional foods and nutraceuticals. Encapsulation technologies have developed as a promising technology to defeat these obstacles by safeguarding bioactive compounds against degradation, enhancing solubility and providing a controlled release. This review paper gives a detailed insight into the encapsulation methods, including spray drying, freeze drying, coacervation & nanoencapsulation but mainly with regard to the effect they have on bioavailability. The food industry use, scaling issues and the prospects of the future are addressed, pointing to the possibility of encapsulation to enrich fruit and vegetable by products. This paper highlights encapsulation as an important instrument to the development of functional foods and the advocacy of sustainable food systems by incorporating the recent discoveries.

INTRODUCTION

Bioactive compounds are naturally occurring molecules found in fruits, vegetables, cereals, and other plant-based sources. They include polyphenols, carotenoids, flavonoids, vitamins, and phytosterols, which are known to exert beneficial effects on human health. These compounds play a vital role in reducing oxidative stress, preventing chronic

diseases, and improving overall wellbeing. Despite their potential, the practical application of bioactive compounds in food systems remains limited due to several inherent challenges. Many bioactive compounds are unstable under processing conditions, sensitive to light and oxygen, and exhibit poor solubility in aqueous environments. As a result,

their bioavailability the proportion of a compound that is absorbed and utilized in the body is often low. The food manufacturing is encountering a great diversity of issues regarding the food safety and the eventual look of the product, including regulation of some contaminants (chemical), microbiological issues or acquisition of physico-chemical & sensory assessment. To address the challenge of these, nanotechnology comes into being to enhance the quality & safety of end product.

Nanotechnology in the field of food science is a relatively new field of study that is significant to the future industry production, in that new properties of the particles derived through the reduction will likely offer better sensory qualities of foods such as color, odour, taste & texture. Moreover, nano substances may be applicable in food preservation besides increasing the storage (Sun et al., 2021). It is stated that some of the new applications of this technology include food packaging and designing of bioactive compounds (BACs) delivery systems. To this end, functional nano capsules are produced through the help of surfactants, reverse micelles and emulsion layers. Moreover, such particles have several beneficial characteristics due to their large surface areas, including increased reactivity, increased aqueous solubility, and efficient absorption; encapsulation methods using nanotechnology received much and expanding interest (Li et al., 2021).

Encapsulation involves a method whereby a bioactive compound (a liquid, solid, gas) is entrapped in a matrix, or inert carrier, most often a polymer. The food or flavor molecules and ingredients are the encapsulated entities covered with a barrier that increases its stability in the specific environment. Better regulation of the bioactive release at the desired physiological point is therefore possible, which increases bioactive stability in food matrices (Rezagholidade Shirvan et al., 2024). Therefore, encapsulation is widely used in various fields of science and industry, such as cosmetics, medicine, pharmaceutical industry and food industry. Usually, it is used to cover unpleasant smells or tastes in food preparations or to change liquid phases to solid ones. Nanoencapsulation produces particularly particles that are less than 100nm. Nanoparticles (<0.2 0.25 m), microparticles (0.25-5 m), and macroparticles (5

m or more) are known as encapsulated nanostructures. The heterogeneity of nanoencapsulation is a main strength, which supports a higher encapsulation efficiency and preferable physicochemical characteristics. This procedure provides an interesting approach to reformatting functional food ingredients, which has a strong impact on the product in terms of processability, bioavailability, and stability ((Hao et al., 2025). This review will also be focused on explaining the nature and mechanism of encapsulations in nanotechnology, to understand the properties that dictate an effective use of nanoparticles, to investigate the key coating materials and bioactive compounds (BACs) and ingredients encapsulated, and to evaluate their uses in food systems. The consequences of encapsulation prolong more than health benefits. In the context of food sustainability, fruit and vegetable by products such as mango peel, citrus waste, and carrot pomace are rich sources of bioactive compounds that are often discarded. Encapsulation provides a pathway to valorize these by products, transforming waste into valuable functional ingredients. This aligns with global efforts to reduce food waste and promote circular economy practices.

BIOAVAILABILITY OF PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS

Phenolic compounds are secondary metabolites, which are common in many foods, fruits, vegetables, cereals, horticultural crops, legumes, and chocolate, in drinks including tea and coffee. Polyphenols, which are defined by the existence of one or more aromatic rings as well as hydroxyl groups, are either flavonoids or nonflavonoids. The overall chemical building block of the major families of flavonoids and nonflavonoids is shown below. The flavonoids are the most common and the most varied subclass of polyphenols. These may be further broken down into flavonols (e.g. myricetin, quercetin, rutin, kaempferol), flavones (e.g. apigenin, Luteolin, tangeretin), flavanones (e.g. hesperetin, hesperidin, naringenin), isoflavones (e.g. genistein, daidzein), and anthocyanidins (e.g. cyanidin, delphinidin, malvidin, pelargonidin). Nonflavonoid polyphenols fall into many different classes, and include stilbenes (e.g. resveratrol), lignans, hydrolyzable tannins and

phenolic acids (including hydroxybenzoic acids and hydroxycinnamic acids) (Ran et al., 2024) Phenolic compounds have lots of health benefits, like fighting cancer and inflammation. They're being used in foods to make them healthier. Flavonoids can stop

cancer cells from growing and even kill them. Studies in animals show that citrus peel extract, which is full of these compounds, can shrink tumors ((Ahmed et al., 2025)

Figure 1. Basic structure of (a) common classes of flavonoids and (b) nonflavonoid-type phenolic compounds.

Phenolic Compound Benefits: Fights free radicals, Reduces inflammation, Fights cancer, Fights viruses and bacteria. Some Key Compounds: Tangeretin: helps with immune response, Sinensetin: helps with swelling, Hesperidin: fights unstable molecules. (Zheng et al.,2025) Phenolic compounds have low utilization, which limits their health benefits. They are not very soluble and can be unstable in the body. This is an issue for lipophilic compounds (Huang & Tariq, 2025). Concerns with Phenolic Compounds: Not very soluble, Unstable, Hard for body to absorb. Impact Change their chemical structure, use special application strategies, use with other nutrients, Use tiny particles to transport them. These Methods such

as: Spray drying, Freeze drying, Coacervation, Nanoencapsulation. Benefits of These Methods are as easier for body to absorb, More efficient health beneficial. (Kalita et al.,2025)

NANOENCAPSULATION OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS & FOOD INGREDIENTS

Numerous valuable nutrients, like essential fatty acids and vitamins, do not dissolve well in water, making them hard to absorb. This creates a barrier for food and supplement makers who want to include in products. Nutrients that are hard to use: Essential fatty acids, Carotenoids, Plant compounds, Vitamins that do not dissolve in water. The impact: They do not dissolve well; Body cannot use them.

Figure 02: Enhancement of stability, functionality and form of food products through nanoencapsulation of BACs.

Nanoencapsulation represents an advanced techniques that protects food constituents from degradation while masking unwanted taste and odor. By minimize particle size, nanoencapsulation enhance the stability, utilization, solubility, and transport of bioactive compounds, hence elevates their functional efficiency. These techniques have effectively soluble lipophilic components, such as carotenoids and antioxidants, in hydrous solutions and fruit-based drinks. In addition, nanoencapsulation has the effect of controlling the release of active ingredients such as phenolic compounds and vitamins thus enhancing the overall quality of the final food product (Kamble et al., 2025). It makes nutrients highly stable, easy for body to absorb, and releases nutrients where need, covers bad tastes or smells. It also used for antioxidants, vitamins, beneficial bacteria, minerals and flavors delivery.

Phenolic Compounds and Carotenoids

Phenolic compounds belong to a general category of plant-derived molecules that include phenolic acids, flavonoids, and many related groups. These compounds have become increasingly impact in the food series because of their antioxidant activity and their potential role in supports human health. Many studies concern regular intake of polyphenols with reduce swelling and low risk of chronic conditions

such as cardiovascular disorders, neurodegenerative diseases, type 2 diabetes, and different type of cancer (Saad et al., 2025).

The antioxidant impact main stems from their ability to neutralize reactive oxygen variety. These advantages, phenolic compounds are more sensitive to environmental factors. Expose to light, oxygen, or heat during processing and storage conditions can lead to degradation. Their effectiveness in the body is limited by low utilization, they may be altered during digestion by pH changes, digestive enzymes, or interactions with other food components. Some phenolics particular flavanols and flavanones a naturally sour taste, which can inhibit the direct use in food formulations (Qu et al.,2025).

Application of encapsulation systems especially at nanoscale has demonstrated potential in addressing the intrinsic challenges and in improving the stability and functional utility of phenolic compounds in food products. An example is the encapsulation of phenolic extracts of the fruit guabiroba with poly (d,l-lactic -co -glycolic acid) through a modified emulsion-evaporation method. Such methods have improved the security of the phenolic components, retained their biological activity up to the time of consumption and offered a controlled release pattern. Encapsulated caffeic acid phenethyl ester, a hydrophobic and functional extract of propolis, in an aqueous system of propylene glycol using sucrose

fatty acid ester and temperature-cycling method. This formula improved its stability in physiological terms and its cancer cell activity (Pereira et al., 2018)

Functional foods research has resulted in the creation of a number of nano-delivery systems of phenolic compounds. Qi et al., (2023) reported the development of nanoparticles composed of chitosan and poly (γ glutamic acid) designed to enhance the oral delivery of tea catechins. These nanostructures can be incorporated into beverages, foods, and dietary supplements to improve stability, bioavailability, and functional efficacy. Most of the well-known health properties of green tea, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and antihypertensive effects, are attributed to catechins; however, their effectiveness in the body is limited by poor absorption and low stability in the gastrointestinal tract (Qi et al., 2023). Nanotechnology-based delivery systems have been shown to enhance the stability, intestinal transport, and bioavailability of tea polyphenols, improving their functional performance in both in vitro and in vivo studies. Biopolymer-based nanoparticles are particularly effective because they protect bioactive compounds, improve absorption, and reduce undesirable interactions in food matrices. Polyphenols also contribute to the technological qualities of foods; for example, chlorogenic acids from green coffee beans interact with proteins, influencing aroma formation, and their encapsulation in cyclodextrin complexes has been used to enhance flavors in bakery and dairy products. Similarly, nanoparticles carrying hydrophobic phenolics such as curcumin and lutein have been developed to improve solubility and expand their application in functional foods (Pateiro et al., 2021).

Essential Oils and Fatty Acids

Plant-derived essential oils (EOs) are broadly acknowledged for their potential antimicrobial effects and are increasingly viewed as natural substitutes for synthetic preservatives. Current research mention that volatile secondary metabolites find extensive applications in food, cosmetic, and pharmaceutical applications due to antibacterial, antifungal, and antioxidant activities. Despite these advantages, their direct incorporate into food systems is often hindered by challenging their poor

solubility in water, rapid volatilization, limit utilization, and instability during processing or storage (Tsitlakidou et al., 2023). To address these limitation nanoencapsulation methods have emerge as effective solutions and improves the functional performance of EOs in food applications. Both food and pharmaceuticals sectors are actively exploring carrier systems that enables the inclusion of small quantities of EOs without compromising sensory or product quality. Encapsulation techniques such as nano emulsions, liposomes, and solid lipid nanoparticles have been successful implement to elevate the stability and activity of plant bioactive compounds. Many essential oils and fish oils possessing strong odors or taste, which restrict their accept in food formulation. (Lin et al.,2019)

Nanoencapsulation provides the both beneficial of masking these undesired sensory attributes while also safeguarding the encapsulated oils from oxidative damage, evaporation, and environmental stresses. It further enables controlled these which prolonging the presence and activity of bioactive compounds over time. The antimicrobial effectiveness of EOs often increases when they are nano encapsulated. For instance, clove essential oil (CEO), rich in eugenol, has been successful incorporated into chitosan nanoparticles via an emulsion-ionic gelation method. These CEO-loaded nanoparticles demonstrated stronger antifungal activity against *Aspergillus Niger* isolated from spoiled pomegranate compared to free, unencapsulated oil. This suggests that CEO-chitosan nanoparticles can serve as a promising natural preservative for food and agricultural applications. Similarly, essential oils obtained from *Cyperus articulatus* were encapsulated in chitosan nanocarriers and demonstrates notable antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*, along with favor stability characteristics require for food and pharmaceutical use. (Hasheminejad et al.,2019)

In addition to antimicrobial applications, nanoencapsulation is also used to preserve the quality of oils used for flavoring. One study focus on encapsulating roasted coffee bean oil using whey protein as the wall material through nano spray drying. Coffee oil is highly prone to oxidation which results in development of undesirable flavors. Encapsulation in the form of nano emulsion

markedly improve its oxidative stability, a benefit attributed to the protective action of whey protein as an emulsifier and the optimized ratio between the oil and material. (Pateiro et al., 2021)

ENCAPSULATION TECHNIQUES

The concept of encapsulation is widely used in food, nutraceutical and pharmaceutical systems to improve the protection, stability and efficiency in the delivery of bioactive components. This allows controlled release of sensitive molecules at the targeted location by protecting the sensitive molecules, thereby reducing degradation, making them easier to deal with, and allowing controlled release. The decision to use encapsulation is mostly determined by the nature of the bioactive compound as well as the intended use (Alu'datt et al.,2022)

Spray-Drying

Spray-drying is among the most established encapsulation techniques valued for its cost effective, scalability, and ability to produce stable powdered formulations. In this process, the active material is first combined with an appropriate wall agent to create a homogenous liquid dispersion. This mixture is then atomized through a fine nozzle into a chamber filled with heated air, where rapid moisture evaporation transforms the droplets into dry microcapsules. (Samborska et al.,2021)

This technique is applicable to a board range of compounds, such as vitamins, oils, flavors, and pigments. Spray-drying offers effective protection against environmental factors and improve the shelf life. Nether less, it typically necessitates water-soluble coat materials and expose heat-sensitive bioactive to moderate thermal effect. (Lu et al.,2021)

Freeze-Drying (Lyophilization)

Freeze-drying is considered a mild a gentle encapsulation method, in which the product is first frozen and then the ice is eliminated through the sublimation under reduce pressure. Since the process does not involve high temperatures, it's particularly suitable for heat sensitive compounds, such as aroma constituents, antioxidants, and probiotics (Coşkun et al.,2024). Freeze drying yields lightweight, porous powders with superior rehydration capacity. Although it offers notable benefits, the process is

slower considerably more costly than spray drying and demand equipment with high consumption. (Rezvankhah et at.,2020)

Extrusion

Extrusion is a process in which a polymer solution containing the bioactive material through a narrow orifice into a gelling medium When sodium alginate is employed the droplets immediate form gel beads upon interaction with calcium ions in the gelling bath. Extrusion is the straightforward technique that works effectively for both water-soluble and fat-soluble compounds while ensuring good stability. Nevertheless, it often results in relatively large capsules with a porous structure, which can permit quicker diffusion of the encapsulated agent. In addition, scaling up the process is difficult due to equipment. (Manzoor et al.,2023; Rani, & Kamble, 2024)

Emulsification

Emulsification involves by dispersing one immiscible liquid into another to form oil-in-water (O/W) or water-in-oil (W/O) emulsions. Emulsifying agents stabilize the droplets, and resulting emulsions may be applied directly or transform into powders using drying processes. (Henao-Ardila et al.,2024)

Emulsification is especially advantage for encapsulating lipid-soluble compounds such as carotenoids, essential oils, and fatty acids. Based on the formulation and processing parameters, this technique can generate microemulsions, nano emulsions, or more sophisticated double emulsions, each providing distinct release and stability characteristics. (Banasaz et al.,2020)

Coacervation

Coacervation involves the phase separation of polymers from a solution resulting in a concentrated layer that's around the active compound. In the case of simple coacervation, a only one polymer is used, while sophisticated coacervation relies on interactions between two caring oppositely charged polymers. The addition of cross-linking agents can be added to enhance the mechanical strength of the resulting capsules. (Timilsena et al.,2019)

Coacervation is capable of achieving high encapsulation efficiency and offers precise regulation

of release profiles. Nevertheless, capsules produce from this method sensitive to pH changes, prone to aggregation, and relatively costly to manufactured on an industrial scale (Yun et al., 2021).

COATING MATERIALS FOR ENCAPSULATION

Choosing the accurate coat material is essential in encapsulation, since it governs the effectiveness of targeted delivery, release, and regulate the accessibility of bioactive substances. A suitable coating should not reactive chemically with the active and must provide strength, stability, flexibility, and barrier protection. For food systems, coatings are further required to be GRAS certified, biodegradable, and protective against environmental challenges (Jahangiri et al., 2024). A broad range of materials are employed in encapsulation, include plant and marine derived polysaccharides, proteins, and lipids. Common utilized examples include gum Arabic, chitosan, and cyclodextrins. In recent years, natural proteins and polysaccharides such as whey protein, soy protein, gelatin, and starch have attracted growing interest, reflecting the shift toward sustainable “green” practices in the food, pharmaceutical, and cosmetic industries. (Palacin, 2022)

Polysaccharides

As coating materials, polysaccharides are widely utilized because they effectively entrap bioactive substances in a solid framework, producing stable capsules. Their resistance to the digestion activity in the upper gastrointestinal organisms makes them specifically appropriate to colon-delivery, where the bioactive absorption is the most effective (Wang et al., 2025).

Starch and its derivatives

Starch is made up of amylose and amylopectin groupings of α -D-glucose and is subject to physical, chemical or enzymatic changes (Nawaz et al., 2020). These treatments improve its oxidation and thermal stress resistance, emulsifying capability, and solubility. The degree of hydrolysis, as the Dextrose Equivalent (DE), is associated with the viscosity and solubility: the higher the DE values, the lower the viscosity and the higher the solubility, the higher the

integrity of the wall material. Maltodextrins which are produced through partial hydrolysis of corn starch are widely used in spray drying, extrusion and fluidized bed granulation due to their thermal stability, tastelessness and digestibility. Inulin is a chicory-derived fructooligosaccharide that acts as a wall ingredient with an added prebiotic effect, enhanced mineral absorption, and ability to form small microcapsules with a low water uptake, which leads to an increase in stability (Qiu et al., 2022).

Plant Exudates

Phytonic substances which are polysaccharide mixtures and exude through plants (gums, resins, latex, and root secretions) have bioactive properties (antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory activity) (Alamgir, 2018). Gum Arabic is a polysaccharide produced by Leguminosai species and it is also commonly employed to develop protective coating around core materials, and it can be used together with other polysaccharides, proteins and modified starches. Other gums are also used, like Karaya, Tragacanth and Mesquite. High-molecular-weight polymers of alpha (1→4) linked D-galacturonic acid (pectins) are commonly used as shell materials in the encapsulation of double emulsions during encapsulation. Soluble soybean polysaccharide (SSP) helps to stabilize emulsions and create film and retain its viscosity in acidic, thermal, and saline environments (Sai et al., 2024).

Proteins

Proteins serve as effectively encapsulation materials own to their biodegradability, biocompatibility, and solubility. Plant derived proteins are particularly favor because of their lower allergenic potential and their suitability for both hydrophilic and hydrophobic bioactive, which they can connect through hydrogen bonding and hydrophobic interacts (Gomes et al., 2021). Soy protein isolates are broadly use to shield sensitive compounds from oxidative damage and to mask undesirable flavors, either independently or in combination with polysaccharides.

Gluten, a byproduct of wheat starch, is value for its ability to form gels and films. Pea and rice proteins provide functional benefits such as emulsion stabilization and foam formation, and they improve

microcapsule development when blended with polysaccharides or alginate/carrageenan. Animal proteins, includes caseins and gelatin, are extensively utilize. Gelatin, derived from collagen, is particular notable for its strong film forming capacity, solubility, and emulsifying properties, making it well suitable for spray drying applications. (Reji et al.,2025)

6. FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Phenolic compounds are well acknowledged for their health enhancing effects, as evidence by extensively scientific research. Their effectiveness in vivo human body, however, depends on their capacity to endure absorption, be released from the food matrix, and subsequently absorbed. Despite notable advances in understanding their bio accessibility and bioavailability, consider undesirable persist, particular concern their behavior during gastrointestinal transiting and their connection with biological systems (Dima et al., 2020). Recently, in vitro absorption systems are broadly applied to prediction the behavior of phenolic compounds within the gastrointestinal tract. Although informative, these systems provide only a simply approximation of human digestion. Encapsulation presents a promising strategy to improve phenolic transform by shielding them from deteriorate, improve stability, and enable the site specific controlled released. Various factors determine the effectiveness of such systems, among which are the chemical diversities of the phenolics, their interactions with dietary factors, the properties of the encapsulation medium, the type of encapsulation strategy, and the activity of the gut microbiota. Due to the complexity of the structure of phenolic substances, future studies must focus on the development of new encasing materials and sophisticated technologies that will be able to help maximize their stability and absorption. The main challenge to large scale industrial use of encapsulation currently is the ability to scale up production in such a way that efficiency and cost effectiveness can still be maintained (Weng et al.,2024). Traditional in vitro models typically use two-dimensional cell cultures, which cannot effectively model the structure and physiology of the human tissues. Further systems like organ on a chip

platform are more realistic because they recapitulate the three-dimensional structure and microenvironment of living organs. These systems allow a closer assessment of transport, metabolic, and phenolic compound interactions, which are similar to those in the human body. Similar advantages may be attained with the microchannel or microreactor technologies which provide better control over the reaction conditions, enhanced safety, simpler scalability, and less reagent and time wastage. Research interest in another area is on sustainable utilization of agro-industries residues. These by-products contain valuable substances in sufficient amounts, contains phenolics and enzymes and are convertible into functional ingredients or encapsulating agents. Solid-state fermentation (SSF) is an environmentally friendly and cost-effective alternative to the conversion of lignocellulosic materials into high-value products. The research shows that using SSF to process phenolic-contaminated phenolic-rich substance by fungi can enhance the liberation and bioavailability of phenolic compounds during digestion. Moreover, there is also the process of enzyme synthesis, including lipases which are needed in simulated digestion processes, in SSF (Karimi et al.,2025).

The lignocellulosic wastes are also getting a lot of investigations as a cheap source of encapsulation materials due to the high polysaccharide contents in them. Fruits peels and processed residues contain pectin, which is a broad and can be extracted and utilized as a gelling agent to encapsulate it. Similarly, the byproducts of the juice industries especially those of citrus can be converted into fiber rich powders, which can be used effectively as wall materials in spray drying process. These green decisions will give guidance on the development of ecofriendly, cost-effective encapsulation systems that would improve the transportation and functional properties of phenolic substances.

7.CONCLUSION

Encapsulation technologies are now critical in the modern science of food by improving stability, bioavailability and targeted delivery of bioactive compounds, especially of fruit and vegetable by-products. These systems protect the sensitive molecules, such as polyphenols, vitamins, and

carotenoids, against a degradation caused by environmental factors, processing methods, or digestive activities. Encapsulation helps to maintain the functional integrity of bioactive compounds and to release them to target and consequently enhance their nutritional and therapeutic performance. In addition to health promotion, the use of agricultural by-products as encapsulation material helps to produce food sustainably because it transforms waste residues into value-added functional ingredients, as circular economy implies. The nutritional gains that accrue to the use of agricultural by-products as encapsulating agents are also another aspect that makes food production sustainable as the residues are converted into improved functional attributes in line with the ideas of a circular economy. The value and effectiveness of encapsulation have been improved significantly by significant breakthroughs in nanotechnology, biopolymer carriers, and novel drying or structuring processes that make these systems appropriate to use in an industrial setting. However, a lot of limitations remain, such as the expensive cost of production, strictness of control conditions, and inconsistency in the level of consumer acceptance. These issues will require the effort of food scientists, engineers, industry leaders, and policymakers. Encapsulation protects bioactive substances against oxidative, thermal, photolytic and enzymatic degradation which makes the bioactive substances release in a more stable and active form to the absorption sites. These systems also increase solubility and dispersibility in aqueous systems and allow site-specific release or control and allow the absorption percentage to increase and heighten biological effects. Nanotechnology has improved encapsulation through the ability to control the size of particles, the characteristics at the surface and the dynamics of release. These innovations have reinforced its position in improving bioavailability besides developing safer and more effective functional food ingredients and pharmaceutical products. To conclude, the encapsulation methods are a scientifically proved and practical approach to the enhancement of stability, protection, and absorption of bioactive agents. Further advancements in this field will push the creation of the next generation of health product with better performance and benefit to consumers.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest among all authors.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

All authors contributed equally for this review article.

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